

HΣPHÆSTUS

Heritage in EuroPe: new technologies in crAft for prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS

Project No. 101095123

Deliverable 6.6

Briefs for business transformation and policymaking

Funded by
the European Union

Document Control Page	
Project acronym	HEPHAESTUS
Project title	Heritage in EuroPe: new techNologies in crAft for prEServing and innovaTing fUtureS
Action	HORIZON EUROPE Culture, Creativity and Inclusive society
Duration	48 months
Grant no.	101095123
Work package	WP6 – Communication, dissemination and impact
Deliverable	Briefs for business transformation and policymaking
Tasks	Task n. 6.6.
Starting Date	01/04/2023
Due Date	31/03/2024
Submission Date	31/03/2024
Document type	Deliverable (D6.6)
Version	2
Dissemination level	Public
Abstract	Through a mapping designed to identify and recommend sub-codes of craftsmanship to policy makers, the report describes the craft sector (in particular, artistic craft) in the four ecosystems associated with the Hephaestus project. The policy brief includes suggestions meant to direct measures for promoting and elevating European handicrafts.
Keywords	Mapping, artistic craft, craft workers, data, NACE codes, statistics
Statement of originality	This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.
Deliverable Lead	Ca' Foscari University of Venice (UNIVE)
Author(s)	Silvia Cacciatore (UNIVE), Manfredi de Bernard (UNIVE)
Point of contact	Manfredi de Bernard, email: manfredi.debernard@unive.it
Reviewers & contributors	CBS, FLV

Document History

Version	Date	Authors, contributors	reviewers,	Changes
D6.6 v0	08/03/2024	Silvia Cacciatore (UNIVE)		First draft
D6.6 v1	09/03/2024	Silvia Cacciatore (UNIVE)		Second draft
D6.6 v2	13/03/2024	Silvia Cacciatore, Manfredi de Bernard (UNIVE)		First version
D6.6 v2.1	18/03/2024	Maria Lusiani, Silvia Cacciatore, Manfredi de Bernard (UNIVE)		Second version
	20/03/2024	Silvia Cacciatore (UNIVE), Alberta Menegaldo (FLV)		Update second version
	21/03/2024	Marta Gasparin (CBS)		
D6.6 v2.2	27/03/2024	Manfredi de Bernard (UNIVE)		Final version

Scheduled updates

The Report is a document which evolves during the lifespan of the project and registers all relevant changes in the life cycle of the HEPHAESTUS project. This document will be updated continuously and finalised in the last month of the project.

Version	Expected by project month (M)
D6.6 v3	24
D6.6 v4	48

Table of contents

Table of contents	4
Table of Tables	5
Table of Figures	5
About HEPHAESTUS	6
1. Executive Summary	7
2. Current classifications and mappings: structure and flaws	9
2.1 NACE classification	9
2.2 ISCO-08 classification	12
3. Proposed guidelines	27
3.1 Towards a Hephaestus definition of craft.....	27
3.2 Methodology.....	29
4. Main deadlines	32
5. Policy Recommendations	33
6. References	34

Table of Tables

Table 1 - Economic activities that relate fully or partly to culture - source: Eurostat (2018)	11
Table 2 - Occupations (ISCO-08 four-digits level) that relate fully (1) or partly (x) to culture (Eurostat, 2018)	14
Table 3 - Detailed list of cultural goods (Eurostat, 2018)	16
Table 4 - Craft professions based on ISCO 08 four-digit level (Eurostat, 2018)	17
Table 5 - UNESCO (1990) craft categories	20
Table 6 - Mapping of heritage craft (Creative & Cultural Skills, 2012).....	26
Table 7 - NUTS classification in relations to the Hephaestus craft ecosystems	31
Table 8 - Main deadlines for the deliverable finalization	32

Table of Figures

Figure 1 - The overlapping definitions of craft	17
Figure 2 - The Hephaestus framework	28

About HEPHAESTUS

Working across the **regional craft ecosystems** of **Bassano del Grappa (IT)**, **Bornholm (DK)**, **Dals Långed (SE)**, and **Venice (IT)**, the overarching ambition of HEPHAESTUS is *to bring together cutting-edge technologies with traditional craft to co-create solutions in the form of a suite of tools, methodologies, and business models to make the future of European craft ecosystems socially, culturally, environmentally, and economically sustainable*. HEPHAESTUS will **test and evaluate solutions** co-created across the four regional craft ecosystems within a “**Future of Craft**” **Green Living Lab** situated in Bornholm, a Danish Island and regional municipality given the title of World Craft Region. Ultimately, the project sets out to create a **sustainable network** (especially including regional realities) of heritage sites, cultural and creative sectors, institutions, universities, local, regional and national authorities, enterprises, and other relevant stakeholders engaged in preservation of craft heritage that will take the project’s results, further adapt and deploy them in a broader range of craft ecosystems, and ensure a long- lasting legacy of the HEPHAESTUS project. The work of HEPHAESTUS is organized around six work packages, each responsible for one specific objective related to the overarching ambition, namely:

Objective 1: Develop new **sustainable business models** for the craft sectors.

Objective 2: Combine **cutting-edge technologies** with craft materials and processes to research and develop new applications and solutions for the digitisation and innovation of the craft sector to improve sustainability and social innovation.

Objective 3: Explore visions for the role of **craft in the future**, integrating emerging technologies and contributing to the circular economy, by engaging craft communities in a participatory ideation process.

Objective 4: Develop a **lifelong learning methodology** and a set of innovative curricula to equip craft-makers with diverse skillsets for innovation.

Objective 5: Establish a **Green Living Lab** for testing the HEPHAESTUS innovations.

Objective 6: To design and operationalise a **bespoke dissemination, communication, and exploitation** strategy.

To achieve these objectives, the consortium includes prominent universities, business schools and a private organization selected for their proven knowledge and expertise on craft heritage, craft materials, and the use of digital technologies and cutting-edge technologies in craft, the proposed innovative and original contributions as well as their trustworthiness. . A unique value added brought to the consortium is represented also by the group of third parties, including craft makers and craft associations, as well as Museums and Municipality representatives, from each of the four regional ecosystems.

HEPHAESTUS Partners	Contact person	Contact
Copenhagen Business School (CBS)	Marta Gasparin / Project Coordinator	mga.bhl@cbs.dk
University of Gothenburg	Elena Raviola	elena.raviola@gu.se
Università degli Studi di Roma Tor Vergata	Luca Pareschi	luca.pareschi@uniroma2.it
Bornholms Regionskommune / BOFA	David Andreas Mana-Ay Christensen	dc@bofa.dk
Università Ca' Foscari Venezia	Fabrizio Panozzo	bauhaus@unive.it
Fablab Venezia	Alberta Menegaldo	alberta@fablabvenezia.org
Comune di Bassano del Grappa	Simone Giotto	hephaestus@comune.bassano.vi.it
WIT Berry	Linda Kimeiša	linda@witberry.lv

1. Executive Summary

Despite the documented cultural and economic value of craft, current categorizations of data regarding crafting organizations are far from adequate. Classifications that prove effective in identifying conventional economic activities often fail when applied to craft. The focus of the present document is on NACE and national equivalents – ATECO, SNI, and Dansk Branchekode DB07 - for Italy, Sweden, and Denmark, respectively. Given its nature, craft ends up being formally considered part of industrial and mass-produced manufacturing sectors. Hard to be confined within exclusive definitions, largely conducted by micro-enterprises operating informally, and more defined by the process rather than the final product, craft falls within the crevices of current classification systems.

Problematically, inadequate identification of craft activities results in underperforming policies that are incapable of understanding the extent of the phenomenon of interest and precisely target craft organizations and their needs. Moreover, from the crafters' perspective, policies and regulations without adequate classification end up misfitting and hampering their activities.

The deliverable's purpose is twofold: on the one hand, to underscore flaws in official classifications and databases and outline guidelines for the project's partners to constitute a robust database despite the limitations of official data sources; on the other hand, to propose a series of policy recommendations precisely addressing the flaws underscored during the data collection process. The document is thus so structured:

- Section 2 presents an overview of the main mapping exercises conducted on a European level. The review is undertaken to gain a broader understanding of the data architecture regarding craft activities, comprehend their limits, and explore how policymakers have addressed them so far.
- Section 3 follows, presenting the guidelines we elaborated to navigate the available data and compensate for their gaps, including a working definition of craft to be adopted by Hephaestus partners. In addition to the reviewed documents and fieldwork, an indispensable element the guidelines lean on is found in the relationship with key members of the ecosystem to adapt structural deficiencies to local opportunities. The section concludes with some structural solutions to minimize the necessity of a dedicated explorative and mapping effort when seeking reliable data on craft in a given ecosystem.
- Section 4 indicates the expected deadlines for each ecosystem to collect and share craft organisations and occupational data.
- Section 5 anticipates the policy recommendations that will follow the completion of the current deliverable course of action.

Disclaimer

This document reflects only the author's view, and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Acknowledgment

HEPHAESTUS project ID 101095123 is funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

2. Current classifications and mappings: structure and flaws

2.1 NACE classification

The NACE codes are a standard classification system for classifying business activities employed at a European level. Each NACE code is subdivided into a hierarchical structure with four levels. The highest-level categories are called sections:

- The first two numbers of the code indicate the division;
- The third number indicates the group;
- The fourth number indicates the class¹.

The struggle to fit within NACE and national equivalent classifications is not exclusive to crafting organizations. Circumscribing the perimeter of all cultural and creative industries (CCIs) presents challenges, as it is not possible to identify a single code as entirely cultural—an issue that craft exacerbates even further. Some creative activities are thus found within NACE codes that, by definition, are not directly attributable to the creative economy but rather belong to other industries.

Eurostat (2018) attempted to analyse individual codes by defining which ones are **entirely**, **partially**, or **not entirely cultural**, periodically updating the indicators. Table 1 lists all the economic activities (NACE Rev. 2 at two-, three- and four-digit levels) that relate fully (1), partly (x), or not entirely (0) to culture.

Code	Description	Cultural Component
18	Printing and reproduction of recorded media	1*
18.1	Printing and service activities related to printing	1*
18.2	Reproduction of recorded media	1*
32	Other manufacturing	x (...)
32.12	Manufacture of jewelry and related articles	1*
32.2	Manufacture of musical instruments	1*
47	Retail trade, except of motor vehicles and motorcycles	x (...)
47.6	Retail sale of cultural and recreation goods in specialised stores	x
47.61	Retail sale of books in specialised stores	1*
47.62	Retail sale of newspapers and stationery in specialised stores	1*

¹ See for instance code C.13.93 corresponding to the “Manufacture of carpets and rugs”, or “*manufacture of textile floor covering: carpets, rugs and mats, tiles*” and also “*manufacture of needle-loom felt floor coverings*”. The class yet excludes *manufacture of mats and matting of plaiting materials*, see 16.29; *manufacture of floor coverings of cork*, see 16.29; *manufacture of resilient floor coverings, such as vinyl, linoleum*, see 22.23.” (Eurostat, 2008).

C.13.93 is thus the class “Manufacture of carpets and rugs”, within the group C.13.9 “Manufacture of other textiles”, in the division C.13 “Manufacture of textiles”, that is part of Section C “Manufacture”. The initial four digits of the code, representing the initial four tiers of the classification system, remain consistent across all European states. However, individual countries have the option to include additional tiers.

47.63	Retail sale of music and video recordings in specialised stores	1*
47.64	Retail sale of sporting equipment in specialised stores	0
47.65	Retail sale of games and toys in specialised stores	0 (...)
58	Publishing activities	x
58.1	Publishing of books, periodicals and other publishing activities	1*
58.11	Book publishing	1
58.12	Publishing of directories and mailing lists	1**
58.13	Publishing of newspapers	1
58.14	Publishing of journals and periodicals	1
58.19	Other publishing activities	1**
58.2	Software publishing	x
58.21	Publishing of computer games	1
58.29	Other software publishing	0
59	Motion picture, video and television programme production, sound recording and music publishing activities	1
59.1	Motion picture, video and television programme activities	1
59.11	Motion picture, video and television programme production activities	1
59.12	Motion picture, video and television programme post-production activities	1
59.13	Motion picture, video and television programme distribution activities	1
59.14	Motion picture projection activities	1
59.2	Sound recording and music publishing activities	1
60	Programming and broadcasting activities	1
60.1	Radio broadcasting	1
60.2	Television programming and broadcasting activities	1
63	Information service activities	x
63.1	Data processing, hosting and related activities; web portals	0
63.9	Other information service activities	x
63.91	News agency activities	1
63.99	Other information service activities n.e.c.	0
71	Architectural and engineering activities; technical testing and analysis	x
71.1	Architectural and engineering activities and related technical consultancy	x
71.11	Architectural activities	1
71.12	Engineering activities and related technical consultancy	0
71.2	Technical testing and analysis	0
73	Advertising and market research	x
73.1	Advertising	x
73.11	Advertising agencies	x
73.12	Media representation	0
73.2	Market research and public opinion polling	0
74	Other professional, scientific and technical activities	x
74.1	Specialised design activities	1
74.2	Photographic activities	1*
74.3	Translation and interpretation activities	1*

74.9	Other professional, scientific and technical activities	0
77	Rental and leasing activities	x (...)
77.2	Renting and leasing of personal and household goods	x
77.21	Renting and leasing of recreational and sports goods	0
77.22	Renting of video tapes and disks	1*
77.29	Renting and leasing of other personal and household goods	0
85	Education	x
85.5	Other education	x
85.51	Sports and recreation education	0
85.52	Cultural education	1
85.53	Driving school activities	0
85.59	Other education	0
90	Creative, arts and entertainment activities	1
90.01	Performing arts	1
90.02	Support activities to performing arts	1
90.03	Artistic creation	1
90.04	Operation of arts facilities	1
91	Libraries, archives, museums and other cultural activities	1**
91.01	Library and archives activities	1
91.02	Museums activities	1
91.03	Operation of historical sites and buildings and similar visitor attractions	1
91.04	Botanical and zoological gardens and nature reserves activities	0

Table 1 - Economic activities that relate fully or partly to culture - source: Eurostat (2018)

The table illustrates the limited number of sectors included in European statistics primarily related to craft, especially the artistic one. The vast majority of codes inherent to manufacturing are indeed not even considered partly cultural and thus excluded from the list.

While the exclusion of craft from cultural economic activities arguably raises questions of value and merit, NACE classifications are still inadequate for classifying craft, as they disregard the process as a classification criterion. Although some codes within Section C – Manufacturing explicitly refer to materials (e.g. (es. 13.2 Weaving of textiles; 16.2 Manufacture of products of wood, cork, straw and plaiting materials; 17.2 Manufacture of articles of paper and paperboard), thus hinting to handicraft, the lack of an explicit reference to the process prevents any further narrowing of the scope.

More broadly, if determining which activities are to be considered partly or fully cultural lacks objective reference — what does "cultural" mean? And "creative"? — craft introduces a second, additional set of definitional questions. Indeed, as admitted by Eurostat and evident in their regular updates of indicators, "what is craft" largely depends on the local context, as it inevitably holds a question of legitimacy that varies in time and space. Furthermore, the borders between craft, the visual arts, and manufacturing appear porous.

2.2 ISCO-08 classification

From an occupational perspective, the International Standard Classification of Occupations (ISCO-08) serves as the primary central classification system used for describing culture (Bina et al., 2012). Despite offering more granularity than NACE, information regarding professions is also dispersed in ISCO-08. Since there is no single code to identify them, the most detailed level (4 digits) often still requires additional criteria. Occasionally, even at the most intricate level, there is no demarcation between vocations that are cultural and those that are not.

As with the ATECO codes, Eurostat identifies several ISCO-08 codes that can be fully or partially attributed to creative workers and occupations (Table 2).

ISCO 08 code	Title	Cultural component
122	Sales, marketing and development managers	x
1221	Sales and marketing managers	0
1222	Advertising and public relations managers	x
1223	Research and development managers	0
134	Professional services managers	x
1341	Childcare services managers	0
1342	Health services managers	0
1343	Aged care services managers	0
1344	Social welfare managers	0
1345	Education managers	0
1346	Financial and insurance services branch managers	0
1349	Professional services managers not elsewhere classified	x
143	Other services managers	x
1431	Sports, recreation and cultural centre managers	x
1439	Services managers not elsewhere classified	0
216	Architects, planners, surveyors and designers	1*
2161	Building architects	1
2162	Landscape architects	1
2163	Product and garment designers	1
2164	Town and traffic planners	1*
2165	Cartographers and surveyors	1*
2166	Graphic and multimedia designers	1
231	University and higher education teachers	x
2310	University and higher education teachers	x
232	Vocational education teachers	x
2320	Vocational education teachers	x
233	Secondary education teachers	x
2330	Secondary education teachers	x
234	Primary school and early childhood teachers	x
2341	Primary school teachers	x

2342	Early childhood educators	0
235	Other teaching professionals	x
2351	Education methods specialists	0
2352	Special needs teachers	0
2353	Other language teachers	1*
2354	Other music teachers	1
2355	Other arts teachers	1
2356	Information technology trainers	0
2359	Teaching professionals not elsewhere classified	0
251	Software and applications developers and analysts	x
2511	Systems analysts	0
2512	Software developers	0
2513	Web and multimedia developers	x
2514	Applications programmers	0
2519	Software developers and analysts not elsewhere classified	0
262	Librarians, archivists and curators	1
2621	Archivists and curators	1
2622	Librarians and related information professionals	1
263	Social and religious professionals	x
2631	Economists	2
2632	Sociologists, anthropologists and related professionals	x
2633	Philosophers, historians and political scientists	x
2634	Psychologists	0
2635	Social work and counselling professionals	0
2636	Religious professionals	0
264	Authors, journalists and linguists	1
2641	Authors and related writers	1
2642	Journalists	1
2643	Translators, interpreters and other linguists	1
265	Creative and performing artists	1
2651	Visual artists	1
2652	Musicians, singers and composers	1
2653	Dancers and choreographers	1
2654	Film, stage and related directors and producers	1
2655	Actors	1
2656	Announcers on radio, television and other media	1
2659	Creative and performing artists not elsewhere classified	1
333	Business services agents	x
3331	Clearing and forwarding agents	0
3332	Conference and event planners	0
3333	Employment agents and contractors	0
3334	Real estate agents and property managers	0
3339	Business services agents not elsewhere classified	x
343	Artistic, cultural and culinary associate professionals	x

3431	Photographers	1
3433	Gallery, museum and library technicians	1
3434	Chefs	0
3435	Other artistic and cultural associate professionals	1
352	Telecommunications and broadcasting technicians	x
3521	Broadcasting and audio-visual technicians	1
3522	Telecommunications engineering technicians	0
441	Other clerical support workers	x
4411	Library clerks	1
4412	Mail carriers and sorting clerks	0
4413	Coding, proof-reading and related clerks	0
4414	Scribes and related workers	0
4415	Filing and copying clerks	0
4416	Personnel clerks	0
4419	Clerical support workers not elsewhere classified	0
511	Travel attendants, conductors and guides	x
5111	Travel attendants and travel stewards	0
5112	Transport conductors	0
5113	Travel guides	x
731	Handicraft workers	x
7311	Precision-instrument makers and repairers	0
7312	Musical instrument makers and tuners	1
7313	Jewellery and precious-metal workers	1
7314	Potters and related workers	1
7315	Glass makers, cutters, grinders and finishers	1
7316	Sign writers, decorative painters, engravers and etchers	1
7317	Handicraft workers in wood, basketry and related materials	1
7318	Handicraft workers in textile, leather and related materials	1
7319	Handicraft workers not elsewhere classified	1
752	Wood treaters, cabinetmakers and related trades workers	x
7521	Wood treaters	0
7522	Cabinetmakers and related workers	x
7523	Woodworking-machine tool setters and operators	0
Notes: * Eurostat's working group on culture statistics reclassified these codes as fully cultural at a meeting in 2016		

Table 2 - Occupations (ISCO-08 four-digits level) that relate fully (1) or partly (x) to culture (Eurostat, 2018)

It is worth noting that cultural statistics on goods and services succeed where NACE and ISCO fail. Combined Nomenclature (CN) codes, the main classification for the European International Trade in Goods Statistics (ITGS), are rather effective in targeting craft products and the occupations they entail. Table 3 indicates the 8-digits codes regarding cultural products according to Eurostat (Eurostat, 2018).

CN (Combined Nomenclature) codes	Craft (handmade fabrics and ornamental articles) Description
5804 30 00	Handmade lace in the piece, in strips or in motifs (excl. fabrics of heading 6002 to 6006)
5805 00 00	Hand-woven tapestries of the type Gobelin, Flanders, Aubusson, Beauvais and the like, and needle-worked tapestries, e.g. petit point, cross-stitch, whether or not made up (excl. Kelem, Schumacks, Karamanie and the like, and tapestries > 100 years old)
5810 10 10	Embroidery on a textile fabric ground without visible ground, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of > Euro 35 per kg
581010 90	Embroidery on a textile fabric ground without visible ground, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of <= Euro 35 per kg
5810 91 10	Embroidery of cotton on a textile fabric ground, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of > Euro 17,50 per kg (excl. embroidery without visible ground)
5810 91 90	Embroidery of cotton on a textile fabric ground, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of <= Euro 17,50, per kg (excl. embroidery without visible ground)
5810 92 10	Embroidery of manmade fibres on a textile fabric base, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of > Euro 17,50 per kg (excl. embroidery without visible ground)
5810 92 90	Embroidery of manmade fibres on a textile fabric base, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of <= Euro 17,50, per kg (excl. embroidery without visible ground)
5810 99 10	Embroidery of materials other than cotton or manmade fibres, on a textile fabric base, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of > Euro 17,50 per kg (excl. embroidery without visible ground)
5810 99 90	Embroidery of materials other than cotton or manmade fibres, on a textile fabric base, in the piece, in strips or in motifs, of a net value of <= Euro 17,50, per kg (excl. embroidery without visible ground)
6002 40 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics, of a width of <= 30 cm, containing >= 5% by weight elastomeric yarn (excl. containing rubber thread, pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, and knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated)
6002 90 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics, of a width of <= 30 cm, containing >= 5% by weight elastomeric yarn and rubber thread or rubber thread only (excl. pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated, and sterile surgical or dental adhesion barriers of subheading 3006.10.30)
6003 10 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics of wool or fine animal hair, of a width of <= 30 cm (excl. those containing by weight >= 5% of elastomeric yarn or rubber thread, and pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, and knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated)
6003 20 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics of cotton, of a width of <= 30 cm (excl. those containing by weight >= 5% of elastomeric yarn or rubber thread, and pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile

	fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, and knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated)
6003 30 10	Raschel lace of synthetic fibres, of a width of ≤ 30 cm (excl. those containing by weight $\geq 5\%$ of elastomeric yarn or rubber thread)
6003 30 90	Knitted or crocheted fabrics of synthetic fibres, of a width of ≤ 30 cm (excl. Raschel lace, those containing by weight $\geq 5\%$ of elastomeric yarn or rubber thread, and pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated, and sterile surgical or dental adhesion barriers of subheading 3006.10.30)
6003 40 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics of artificial fibres, of a width of ≤ 30 cm (excl. those containing by weight $\geq 5\%$ of elastomeric yarn or rubber thread, and pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated, and sterile surgical or dental adhesion barriers of subheading 3006.10.30)
6003 90 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics of a width of ≤ 30 cm (excl. of cotton, man-made fibres, wool or fine animal hair, those containing by weight $\geq 5\%$ of elastomeric yarn or rubber thread, and pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated, and sterile surgical or dental adhesion barriers of subheading 3006.10.30))
6004 10 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics, of a width of > 30 cm, containing $\geq 5\%$ by weight elastomeric yarn (excl. containing rubber thread, pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, and knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated)
6004 90 00	Knitted or crocheted fabrics, of a width of > 30 cm, containing $\geq 5\%$ by weight elastomeric yarn and rubber thread or rubber thread only (excl. pile fabrics, incl. "long pile", looped pile fabrics, labels, badges and similar articles, and knitted or crocheted fabrics, impregnated, coated, covered or laminated)
4420 90 10	Wood marquetry and inlaid wood (excl. statuettes and other ornaments, articles of furniture, lamps and lighting fittings and parts thereof)
9601 10 00	Worked ivory and articles of ivory
9601 90 00 2011	Worked bone, tortoiseshell, horn, antlers, coral, mother-of-pearl and other animal carving material, and articles of these materials, n.e.s. (excl. ivory)
9601 90 10	Worked coral, natural or agglomerated, and articles of coral,
9601 90 90	Worked bone, tortoiseshell, horn, antlers, mother-of pearl and other animal carving material and articles of these materials, n.e.s. (excl. ivory or coral)
6913 10 00	Statuettes and other ornamental articles of porcelain or china
6913 90 10	statuettes and other ornamental articles of common pottery
6913 90 93	Statuettes and other ornamental articles of earthenware or fine pottery
7018 90 90	Statuettes and other ornaments of lamp-worked glass (excl. imitation jewellery)

Table 3 - Detailed list of cultural goods (Eurostat, 2018)

Within the limited possibilities offered by European statistics to identify data on craft, the CN codes (Table 3) yet enable the filtering of cultural occupations (Table 2) to identify those relevant to craft workers (Table 4).

ISCO-08	Craft Profession
7312	Musical instrument makers and tuners
7313	Jewelry and precious-metal workers
7314	Potters and related workers
7315	Glass makers, cutters, grinders and finishers
7316	Sign writers, decorative painters, engravers and etchers
7317	Handicraft workers in wood, basketry and related materials
7318	Handicraft workers in textile, leather and related materials
7319	Handicraft workers not elsewhere classified

Table 4 - Craft professions based on ISCO 08 four-digit level (Eurostat, 2018)

2.3 Previous mapping attempts

The challenges of fitting craft within the confines of current classifications are underscored by the current framework of the European Union regarding cultural statistics (see Bina et al., 2012), which explicitly leaves a gap regarding the NACE rev.2 code for craft (p. 73). Unfortunately, previous European projects and academic publications dedicated to mapping Cultural and Creative Industries (CCIs) and/or crafts also do not convincingly address the issue. Projects such as COCO4CCI (Università Ca' Foscari Venezia, 2019), DIVA (luav DIVA Project Team, 2019), and InduCCI (Weber & Duarte, 2020), which have a broader scope, do not include craft within the CCIs framework. Others, such as the Mingei project or the work of Bertacchini and Borrione (2013), explicitly acknowledge the limitations of the NACE classifications but do not propose an alternative approach to compensate for this deficiency.

Moreover, and not surprisingly, many of these projects delineated these notions differently (see Figure 1). The Mingei project (FORTH, 2020) introduces the topic of **heritage crafts** as a set of artifacts, materials, and craft tools, and understands crafts as a form of intangible cultural heritage.

Figure 1 - The overlapping definitions of craft

Another relevant study on the topic refers to heritage craft as a set of *"practices which employ manual dexterity and skill and an understanding of traditional materials, designs and techniques in order to make, repair, restore or conserve buildings, other structures, modes of transport, or more general, portable objects."* (Creative & Cultural Skills, 2012: 6).

The "conservative" element of the definition above originates from UNESCO's perspective on **traditional crafts** within the broader family of intangible cultural heritage, which encompasses all non-material aspects of culture—ephemeral products such as stories, music, and language itself, as well as the forms of knowledge and skills that contribute to cultural vitality and continuity. This includes the wide range of traditional craft skills that, once lost, may be almost impossible to regain.

Others rely on a perspective on craft less versed on the conservation of the heritage and more on the creative act it implies. For example, the RICHES project (2016) recognizes craft as *"a distinctive set of knowledge, skills and attitudes, centred on a process of reflective engagement with the material and digital world"* (Schwarz & Yair, 2012), characterized by the application of haptic skills and manually controlled tools. The project's authors thus draw an additional distinction between contemporary crafts, characterized by original designs and enhancing the artistic intervention of the maker, and traditional or heritage crafts, which rely on inherited techniques and designs, emphasizing authenticity rather than originality.

Nonetheless, the line of distinction between contemporary craft and traditional craft is exceedingly blurred and trespasses the design, visual and/or applied arts domain.

Eurostat (Bina et al., 2012) thus precisely argues for the establishment of the **art crafts** domain in one effort to recognise the potential but not essential traditionality of craft. The notion precisely refers to original artistic and cultural products, thus stressing the aesthetic dimension and the non-industrial creation process.

Furthermore, when defining the sector for statistics' sake, Eurostat adopt the International Trade Center (ITC) and UNESCO definition of Crafts, or artisanal products, described as *"those produced by artisans, either completely by hand or with the help of hand-tools or even mechanical means, as long as the direct manual contribution of the artisan remains the most substantial component of the finished product. The special nature of artisanal products derives from their distinctive features, which can be utilitarian, aesthetic, artistic, creative, culturally attached, decorative, functional, traditional, religiously and socially symbolic and significant"* (International Trade Centre UNCTAD/WTO (Switzerland), 1997: 6).

UNESCO thus identifies **six broad categories of artisanal products based on the materials used**: Baskets/wickers/vegetable fibre-works; Leather; Metal; Pottery; Textiles and Wood (Etienne-Nugue, 1990). The guide also identifies complementary categories comprising materials in craft production that are either very specific to a given area, or rare, or difficult to work, such as stone, glass, ivory, bone, shell, mother-of-pearl etc.

Extra categories are also identified when different materials and techniques are applied at the same time and refer to decorations, jewelry, musical instruments, toys, and works of art. Many crafts objects are produced industrially; nevertheless, FCS considers the products, that have a traditional character (pattern, design, technology, or material) as part of the FCS. Contemporary crafts are not in Visual Arts and Crafts, but are included in Domain F, the Design and Creative Services domain. The resulting classification (Table 5) represents the main basis for defining European sector statistics on craft.

Craft Category	Description
Basketry	(vegetable fibres) Possible secondary categories: constructions of straw or other vegetable materials, toys, costumes, decorations, musical instruments.
Textiles	(vegetable or animal fibres) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • raw materials: bark, raffia, skins • fashioned or woven materials: cotton, linen, silk, wool. • decorated materials: dyeing, embroidery, applique work.
Pottery	(earth) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • dried earth. • natural baked earth. • glazed, enamelled, varnished baked earth Possible secondary categories: constructions made of earth, toys, musical instruments, decorations.
Wood	(various vegetable materials) Possible secondary categories: gourds, nuts and various shells.
Metal	iron, copper, alloys, precious metals.
Leather	(various skins from animals - cattle, sheep, reptiles, fish, crocodiles).
Complementary Categories	Some countries or regions also use much more unusual materials in their craft production, materials that are either very specific to the area, rare or difficult to work. These materials could form extra categories in the countries where they are used. For the record: Stone (rocks and precious stones), glass, ivory, bone, horn, shell, seashells, mother-of-pearl, etc.
Extra Categories	Where the research is centred on a more specific theme, the classification may have to use “extra categories” embracing several different materials and techniques at the same time. The components of these categories can already be found in the main categories, so all that has to be done is to regroup them in order to highlight the most important aspect. For example, the following could be included in extra categories: The home, traditional architecture: techniques using straw, earth, wood. Wall decoration, signs: various supports and decorative techniques using traditional or modern colouring matter.

	<p>Toys, games: techniques using straw, earth, wood, iron, textiles.</p> <p>Musical instruments, dance accessories: articles made of wood, metal, straw, leather.</p> <p>Costumes, accessories, hair ornaments: techniques using skins, textiles, straw, metal.</p> <p>Recycling crafts: articles made from a wide variety of materials worked according to traditional techniques.</p>
--	---

Table 5 - UNESCO (1990) craft categories

One of the first up-to-date reports that tries to focus on the craft sector is *Mapping Heritage Craft. The economic contribution of the Heritage Craft sector in England* (Creative & Cultural Skills, 2012). The report uses the SIC (Standard Industrial Classification) industrial activity classification system, comparable to NACE adopted mainly in the United States and UK. Although the report refers to the United Kingdom, it is nonetheless helpful attempt to identify such an "unclearly defined and sometimes hard-to-reach sector, made up of a proliferation of micro-businesses" (Ibid.: 2).

Craft is there defined as a set of "Practices which employ manual dexterity and skill and an understanding of traditional materials, designs and techniques in order to make, repair, restore or conserve buildings, other structures, modes of transport, or more general, portable objects." (Ibid.: 1).

On these assumptions, the report follows with a list of the practices that can be traced back to heritage craft are:

- "Understanding of and engagement with materials
- The application of haptic skills and hand-controlled tools
- The honing of skills learned over time
- One-off or relatively small batch rather than mass production
- Maker impact on conception, design and aesthetics of finished product
- Cultural embedding of finished product." (Ibid.: 19).

The informative richness of the report lies in presenting a list of specific craft practices for a given material and then subdividing the materials/composites into several subgroups, based on the type of item produced or the process undertaken.

Sector	Sub-sector	UKSIC07	SIC description
Animal	Equine leather	1511	Tanning and dressing of leather; dressing and dyeing of fur
	Leather preparation dressing and dyeing of fur	1511	Tanning and dressing of leather;
	Leather clothing and accessories	1520	Manufacture of footwear
	Making, restoring and conserving other leather objects	1511	Tanning and dressing of leather; dressing and dyeing of fur
	Leather luggage	1512	Manufacture of luggage, handbags and the like, saddlery and harness

	Taxidermy	3299	Other manufacturing not elsewhere classified (n.e.c.)
Clay	Clay construction, building, restoration and conservation	2331	Manufacture of ceramic tiles and flags
	Making, finishing, restoring and conserving clay objects	2331	Manufacture of ceramic tiles and flags
	Tile making	2331	Manufacture of ceramic tiles and flags
	Making, finishing, restoring and conserving clay objects	2341	Manufacture of ceramic household and ornamental articles
	Making, finishing, restoring and conserving clay objects	9529	Repair of other personal and household goods
	Tile installation	4339	Other building completion and finishing
	Glass	Decoration, e.g. engraving, painting	9003
Glass construction, building, restoration and conservation		4334	Painting and glazing
Making, fabrication and restoration of glass objects		2312	Shaping and processing of flat glass
Making, fabrication and restoration of glass objects		2313	Manufacture of hollow glass
Making, fabrication and restoration of glass objects		2319	Manufacture and processing of other glass, including technical glassware
Stained glass		2312	Shaping and processing of flat glass
Stained glass		2313	Manufacture of hollow glass
Guns		Gunsmithing	2540
	Gunsmithing	3311	Repair of fabricated metal products
Instruments	Making and restoring clocks and barometers	2651	Manufacture of instruments and appliances for measuring, testing and navigation
	Making and restoring musical instruments	9529	Repair of other personal and household goods
	Making and restoring musical instruments	3319	Repair of other equipment
	Making and restoring musical instruments	3220	Manufacture of musical instruments

	Making and restoring clocks and barometers	9525	Repair of watches, clocks and jewellery
	Making and restoring clocks and barometers	2652	Manufacture of watches and clocks
Jewellery	Jewellery making	3213	Manufacture of imitation jewellery and related articles
Metal	Architectural metalwork	2511	Manufacture of metal structures and parts of structures
	Architectural metalwork	2512	Manufacture of doors and windows of metal
	Blacksmiths and forgers	2562	Machining
	Decorative and ornamental metalwork	2451	Casting of iron
	Decorative and ornamental metalwork	2512	Manufacture of doors and windows of metal
	Decorative and ornamental metalwork	2550	Forging, pressing, stamping and rollforming of metal; powder metallurgy
	Decorative and ornamental metalwork	2572	Manufacture of locks and hinges
	Fabricated metalwork	2591	Manufacture of steel drums and similar containers
	Farrier	162	Support activities for animal production
	Foundry	2550	Forging, pressing, stamping and roll forming of metal; powder metallurgy
	Hand tools, e.g. knives, cutlery	2571	Manufacture of cutlery
	Hand tools, e.g. knives, cutlery	2573	Manufacture of tools
	Hand tools, e.g. knives, cutlery	3311	Repair of fabricated metal products
	Leadwork	4391	Roofing activities
	Leadwork	4399	Other specialised construction activities
Metal furniture makers	3101	Manufacture of office and shop furniture	

	Metal furniture makers	3109	Manufacture of other furniture
	Wrought iron	2512	Manufacture of doors and windows of metal
	Wrought iron	2812	Manufacture of fluid power equipment
Paint	Decoration	4334	Painting and glazing
Paper	Calligraphy and illumination	9003	Artistic creation
	Papermaking and paper shaping	1712	Manufacture of paper and paperboard
	Papermaking and paper shaping	1724	Manufacture of wallpaper
	Papermaking and paper shaping	1729	Manufacture of other articles of paper and paperboard n.e.c
	Printing, pressing and bookbinding	1812	Other printing
	Printing, pressing and bookbinding	1813	Pre-press and pre-media services
	Printing, pressing and bookbinding	1814	Binding and related services
Plaster	Plastering	4331	Plastering
Precious metals	Engraving and finishing	1814	Binding and related services
	Engraving and finishing	2561	Treatment and coating of metals
	Engraving and finishing	3109	Manufacture of other furniture
	Engraving and finishing	3212	Manufacture of jewellery and related articles
	Engraving and finishing	9525	Repair of watches, clocks and jewellery
	Goldsmithing and silversmithing	9525	Repair of watches, clocks and jewellery
	Goldsmithing and silversmithing	3212	Manufacture of jewellery and related articles
Stone	Bricklaying	4399	Other specialised construction activities n.e.c.
	Carving and letter cutting	1629	Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials
	Dry stone walling	4399	Other specialised construction activities

			n.e.c.
	Stonemasonry	4399	Other specialised construction activities n.e.c.
Textiles	Making, restoring and conserving clothing and accessories	1413	Manufacture of other outerwear
	Making, restoring and conserving clothing and accessories	1414	Manufacture of underwear
	Making, restoring and conserving clothing and accessories	1419	Manufacture of other wearing apparel and accessories
	Making, restoring and conserving clothing and accessories	9529	Repair of other personal and household goods
	Making, restoring and conserving furnishings	1392	Manufacture of made-up textile articles, except apparel
	Making, restoring and conserving other textiles, e.g. felt, sails, nets, ropes	1394	Manufacture of cordage, rope, twine and netting
	Making, restoring and conserving other textiles, e.g. felt, sails, nets, ropes	3319	Repair of other equipment
	Making, restoring and conserving textile products	1399	Manufacture of other textiles n.e.c.
	Spinning, weaving and dyeing	1310	Preparation and spinning of textile fibres
	Spinning, weaving and dyeing	1320	Weaving of textiles
	Spinning, weaving and dyeing	1330	Finishing of textiles
	Tailoring and dressmaking	1413	Manufacture of other outerwear
	Toys & automata	Toys & automata	3240
Vehicles	Vehicle manufacture and restoration – boat	3011	Building of ships and floating structures

	Vehicle manufacture and restoration – boat	3012	Building of pleasure and sporting boats
	Vehicle manufacture and restoration – boat	3315	Repair and maintenance of ships and boats
	Vehicle manufacture and restoration – cars	3099	Manufacture of other transport equipment n.e.c.
	Vehicle manufacture and restoration – cars	3317	Repair and maintenance of transport equipment n.e.c.
Wood & plant	Antique restoration and repair	9529	Repair of other personal and household goods
	Basketry	1629	Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials
	Basketry	9529	Repair of other personal and household goods
	Brooms and brushes	3291	Manufacture of brooms and brushes
	Carpenters and joiners	1623	Manufacture of other builders' carpentry and joinery
	Carpenters and joiners	4332	Joinery installation
	Carpenters and joiners	4399	Other specialised construction activities n.e.c.
	Furniture and cabinet makers	3101	Manufacture of office and shop furniture
	Furniture and cabinet makers	3109	Manufacture of other furniture
	Furniture and cabinet repair/restoration	9524	Repair of furniture and home furnishings
	Ladder manufacturer	1629	Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials

	Making and finishing other wooden objects	1629	Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials
	Picture framing and restoration	1629	Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials
	Picture framing and restoration	4778	Other retail sale of new goods in specialised stores
	Sculptors and wood carvers	1629	Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials
	Thatching	4391	Roofing activities
	Woodturning	1629	Manufacture of other products of wood; manufacture of articles of cork, straw and plaiting materials

Table 6 - Mapping of heritage craft (Creative & Cultural Skills, 2012)

These prior works, all in all, offer only partial guidelines to address the limitations of official categorization, neither theoretically nor pragmatically. Therefore, the following section present Hephaestus' understanding of craft; it then draws on the few mapping efforts which employ a more robust methodology, such as the work of Viganò et al. (2023), the Measuring CCS Consortium Report (2022) and the Mapping Heritage Craft (2012), to develop a series of guidelines that integrate the limited NACE categorization with secondary sources.

3. Proposed guidelines

As we have seen, the current European mappings fail to fully reach and identify the arts and crafts sector, and Eurostat also acknowledges that as “*the European statistical classifications do not take into account art crafts activities as specific ones. Distinction between handcrafted products or machine-made crafts does not appear (except for two products, handmade lace (CN 5804 3000) and hand-woven tapestries (CN 5805 00 00): it is therefore not possible to identify the traditional activities related to art crafts within the NACE classification (only industrial activities are listed). The products classification, CPA [Classification of Products by Activities, ed.], does not neither allow to distinguish the method of production used (hand-made as compared to industrial). The measure of activities and products of art crafts is impossible but by estimating within each industrial activity the proportion of traditional ones.*” (Bina et al., 2012: 336).

This note is of fundamental importance because it recognises the limitations of existing NACE codes and classifications of cultural industries that include craft. This clearly acknowledges the difficulty of statistical mapping, through NACE codes, the arts and crafts sector in Europe.

The goal of our research is to bridge this gap by making it possible to reconstruct the entire aggregate of artistic crafts. Through a qualitative and quantitative methodology, we intend to elaborate NACE sub-codes within each category attributable to craft, to identify and map the entire artistic crafts sector and suggest strategic guidelines to policy makers for their incorporation into European mapping methodologies.

As a significant aspect of the NACE-equivalent limitations arises from overlooking the peculiarities of crafters compared to conventional economic activities, it was essential to directly engage crafters. Conducting qualitative data collection in parallel proved extremely beneficial for our understanding, shedding light not only on the theoretical inconsistencies of the classification but also on how it both connects with and hampers the crafters' activity. Beyond its empirical significance, incorporating crafters' perspectives directly is crucial to avoiding the perpetuation of current classification flaws, which arguably stem from a limited understanding of crafters' everyday experiences. Thus, based on the fieldwork and dialogue with practitioners, we outline in the following sections both Hephaestus' definition of craft and a series of methodological guidelines to identify valuable data sources, collect data, and address the formal criticalities elaborated above.

3.1 Towards a Hephaestus definition of craft

Defining craft is not merely a theoretical exercise but has concrete methodological implications (in terms of the scope of analysis and data collection) and policy implications. Thus, it is necessary for Hephaestus partners to build on a shared understanding of craft. Therefore, acknowledging the cultural diversity of the Hephaestus ecosystems and drawing on the insights from the ongoing fieldwork, we propose the following Hephaestus umbrella definition of craft (note: working definition, Figure 2):

*Craft as the form of manufacturing - from Latin: manus (hand) and facere (making) - in which the components of **manual work**, mastering of **tools and technique**, knowledge of the **materials** meet with an **intentional symbolic value**, and become an object. This ranges from individual productions in small ateliers to component productions in larger manufacturing processes.*

Figure 2 - The Hephaestus framework

Although pinpointing a shared definition is a necessary premise for the mapping exercise we conduct, it does not dispel the challenges mentioned above regarding CCIs and NACE codes. As the process of crafting necessitates substantial manual input from the craft maker to be considered as such, NACE classifies economic activities based on the final product inevitably grouping together both craft-based and non-craft-based activities. Moreover, the initial data collected during the fieldwork underscored challenges perceived by the crafters themselves when facing NACE-equivalent classifications. For example, the interviews so far conducted in Venice revealed that crafters employing multiple materials hardly fit into a single ATECO code (NACE-equivalent classification). Consequently, they must either limit their activities to those within the boundaries of the chosen code or proceed informally. Read for instance the quote below of a jewelry maker working with paper as their main material:

"I started with an idea which then changed because I came up against the Italian bureaucracy: I was planning to open a shop just dedicated to paper jewelry and to mix goldsmithing with paper craft, [but] if one practices goldsmithing, from an administrative point of view one becomes a goldsmith [which implies taxation on the estimated earnings of a goldsmith ed.] [...] and so I said to myself, 'my business will never hold up, let's change it completely.'"

This testimony reports the difficulty of choosing between a NACE 17.29 and 25.99 neither of which, however, are included in traditional mappings on creative industries (Table 1). Thus, based on the initial and yet promising course of action taken in Venice, which allowed for the collection of a comprehensive database regarding craft organizations, both in breadth and depth, we abstracted some guidelines in Section 3.2 for the other partners to adapt to their national context.

3.2 Methodology

Step 1: data collection from existing registers

Our guidelines **start from collecting the NACE-coded data from Chamber of Commerce (CoC)** or equivalent body. Not to exclude any activity a priori, we invite partners to hold an inclusive perspective on the NACE codes to collect, with possibly the exclusion of some areas (e.g. transport, food and/or wellness). The data should ideally contain all relevant information on craft enterprises registered in the CoC (and at least the following):

- NACE code;
- Company name;
- Location at NUTS 3 level (see Table 4 below);
- Main activity;
- Number of employees;
- Year of foundation;
- Website.

Partners should also collect **ISCO-08 data on craft workers** in the ecosystems through databases of local, regional or European statistical offices. This data should identify craft occupations and geographies (location) according to the Eurostat classification.

Step 2: data cleaning and qualitative research integration

As anticipated, the initial dataset will probably be composed of both **overly broad categories and incomplete information** - not all craft organisations are indeed registered to the CoC. The following step should thus aim at:

- Firstly, extract from the too-broad CoC NACE-coded registry the subset of organisations that specifically engage with artistic craft;
- Secondly, individuate those organisations the CoC and official data sources do not capture, e.g. those formally considered hobbyists.

Successfully accomplishing both tasks requires reaching out to ecosystem members to collect additional primary and secondary data through interviews, questionnaires, and integrating further datasets within a collaborative framework. As an illustration, in the Venetian ecosystem, interviewing crafters was necessary to understand the practical, everyday obstacles of the NACE classification from the crafter's perspectives; multiple meetings with the two local craft associations – CNA and Confartigianato – proved instrumental in granting access to their databases of associates and enhancing our understanding of the local legal environment; participating in fairs and local events, and through snowballing, we reached non-represented crafters and those formally not recognized as enterprises. Integrative data sources and possible interlocutors, include but are not limited to:

- Crafters and their representatives;
- Sectoral craft organisations and observatories;

- International, national or regional organisations production non-official statistics;
- Projects undertaken by European organisations;
- Academies and universities;
- Private consultancy firms procuring specific sectoral studies;

For occupational data, the following may specifically prove useful:

- Tax agencies;
- National social and welfare institutions.

We reiterate that the dialogue with ecosystem members is not only valuable for data collection but also essential to our research interest in individuating classifications' inconsistencies. We also encourage researchers to be inclusive and receptive to various parts of the ecosystem and voices that are functional in the quest for documents and a grounded understanding of NACE codes within the crafters' everyday experience, not limiting their scope to official documents and sources only. Moreover, with the intention of keeping these guidelines as an iterative work in progress, we invite partners to enrich them and the theoretical framework by providing pointers to useful documents and data resulting from fieldwork that other partners may benefit from.

Step 3: data display in synthetic tables and report to UNIVE

The data collected from this mixed approach (selective data from existing registers and integrated data from ad hoc investigation – steps 1 and 2) should be presented in synthetic tables in a data format that allows for a numerical synthesis of the entire dataset. Ideally, each entry should include at least:

- Organization name;
- NACE code;
- Location at NUTS 3 level;
- Main activity;
- Number of employees;
- Year of foundation;
- Representative association, if present.

Regarding occupational ISCO-08 data the resulting dataset should include at least:

- Number of workers related to the ISCO-08 classification and retrieved through matching with the relevant NACE code provided by the CoC;
- Data on Craft associated workers and professionals.

Working with different ecosystems requires one shared regional analysis level that allows us to adapt both the data on the organizations and workers. We recommend the partners to organize data on the NUTS classification (Table 7) provided by the European Union (2022).

CODE	NUTS1	NUTS 2	NUTS 3
ITH	Nord-Est Italy		
ITH3		Veneto	
ITH32			Vicenza (Cities) Bassano del Grappa (Municipalities)
ITH35			Venice (Metropolitan area)
DK0	Denmark		
DK014			Bornholm (Island area)
SE23	Western Sweden		
SE232			Göteborg (Cities) Dals Langed/ Fengersfors (Municipalities)

Table 7 - NUTS classification in relations to the Hephaestus craft ecosystems

At the end of the process, the Hephaestus partners related to the different craft ecosystems—UGOT for Dals Långed and Fengersfors, CBS and BOFA for Bornholm—will provide UNIVE with the data related to artistic craft enterprises to be collected and systematized in this report.

4. Main deadlines

The deliverable in its final version will contain an analysis of data on artistic craft in Europe, obtained through the collaboration of the Hephaestus partnership. The partners will provide UNIVE, according to the deadlines indicated in Table 5, with short reports containing the extraction of NACE and ISCO data related to the artistic craft sector following the guidelines above.

PARTNERS	INFORMATION TO PROVIDE	DEADLINE
1) UNIVE, FLV 2) UGOT 3) CBS, BOFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Legal framework related to artistic craft. Scientific literature and results of other European projects related to craft mapping. Report about craft NACE/ISCO codes from Chambers of commerce 	M18 (30/09/2024)
1) UNIVE 2) GOT 3) CBS, BOFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report about craft NACE/ISCO codes matched with data from Craft associations members 	M20 (30/11/2024)
1) UNIVE 2) GOT 3) CBS, BOFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Identification of a first group of NACE/ISCO data about artistic craft organizations 	M22 (31/01/2025)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Update of the deliverable version 	M24 (31/03/2025)
1) UNIVE 2) GOT 3) CBS, BOFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report about on-desk research, questionnaires, qualitative interviews to circumscribe the organizations closely related to the artistic craft 	M32 (30/11/2025)
1) UNIVE 2) GOT; 3) CBS, BOFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Report about all the NACE/ISCO codes related to artistic craft in the ecosystems 	M36 (31/03/2026)
1) UNIVE 2) GOT 3) CBS, BOFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Indication about artistic craft organization and workers not mapped through official statistics 	M40 (31/05/2026)
1) UNIVE, FLV 2) GOT 3) CBS, BOFA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integration of scientific literature and results of other European projects that can help in the drafting of recommendations for policy makers 	M42 (30/09/2027)
1) UNIVE	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Final version of the deliverable 	M48 (31/03/2027)

Table 8 - Main deadlines for the deliverable finalization

5. Policy Recommendations

The document will provide policy recommendations aimed at enhancing the role of craft sectors in cultural statistics and public funding. In addition, we propose to accompany the guidelines for identifying new codes and definitions with some suggestions on how to overcome the inevitable barriers created by the definitions themselves, with a view to rewarding innovation and multidisciplinary. These policy guidelines will be formulated based on the data and information collected by the Hephaestus Partnership throughout its lifetime. They will also be informed by the ability of each partner involved to build networks within their respective ecosystems, fostering profitable dialogues with institutions, organizations related to the cultural sector, and beyond.

The objective is to raise awareness among policymakers about the unique characteristics of the artistic craft sector and to help them understand the most effective ways to strengthen the sector through targeted funding, aligning with UNESCO's call for its protection. The Hephaestus Project is dedicated to promoting the adoption of additional legal measures, such as the protection of intellectual property and the registration of patents or copyrights, to safeguard the craft community and its knowledge as cultural heritage.

6. References

- Bertacchini, E. E., & Borrione, P. (2013). The Geography of the Italian Creative Economy: The Special Role of the Design and Craft-based Industries. *Regional Studies*, 47(2), 135-147. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00343404.2011.628652>
- Bina, V., Chantepie, P., Deroin, V., Frank, G., Kommel, K., Kotynek, J., & Philippe, R. (2012). *European Statistical System Network on Culture: Final report*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/341465/3199631/essnet-culture.pdf/a6518128-69b3-4d89-82b8-060a3ad0d1d5>
- Creative & Cultural Skills. (2012). *Mapping Heritage Craft: The economic contribution of the Heritage Craft sector in England*. <https://heritagecrafts.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/2020/05/Mapping-Heritage-Craft-2012.pdf>
- Etienne-Nugue, J. (1990). Crafts: methodological guide to the collection of data. In *Ten Year Plan of Action for the Development of Crafts in the World 1990-1999*. UNESCO. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000088895>
- Eurostat. (2008). *NACE Rev. 2 – Statistical classification of economic activities in the European Community*. Publications Office.
- Eurostat. (2018). *Guide to Eurostat culture statistics*. <https://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/documents/3859598/9433072/KS-GQ-18-011-EN-N.pdf/72981708-edb7-4007-a298-8b5d9d5a61b5?t=1544174403000>
- FORTH. (2020). *MINGEI: Scientific protocol for craft representation*. <https://www.mingei-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/06/D1.3.pdf>
- International Trade Centre UNCTAD/WTO (Switzerland). (1997). *International Symposium on Crafts and the International Market: Trade and Customs Codification; final report*. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000111488>
- Iuav DIVA Project Team. (2019). *DIVA - Mapping Methodology, Users' Needs and SWOT Analysis*.
- RICHES Project. (2016). *Towards a Craft Revival: Recalibrating Social, Cultural, Economic and Technological Dynamics*. https://resources.riches-project.eu/wp-content/uploads/2016/04/EUROPEAN-POLICY-BRIEF_Craft_final.pdf
- Schwarz, M., & Yair, K. (2012). *Making Value: craft & the economic and social contribution of makers*. https://www.craftscouncil.org.uk/documents/878/Making_value_2010.pdf
- The Measuring CCS Consortium. (2022). *Final Report - Measuring the Cultural and Creative Sectors in the EU*. <https://www.measuring-ccs.eu/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/The-Measuring-CCS-Consortium-publishes-the-Final-Report-Measuring-the-Cultural-and-Creative-Sectors-in-the-EU.pdf>
- Università Ca' Foscari Venezia. (2019). *COCO4CCI: Regional Mapping Italy*.
- Viganò, F., England, L., & Comunian, R. (2023). Connecting craft, design and the wood industry in South Tyrol: From clusters to creative ecosystem. *Journal of Rural Studies*, 104, 103149. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jrurstud.2023.103149>
- Weber, K., & Duarte, T. (2020). *InduCCI: CCI Policies on European Level*.

